

Semiclassical Approach to Quantum Oscillator Ground State Energy with Moyal Product Part II

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In (1), it is argued that if the classical energy of an oscillator $E = pp/2 + wwxx/2$ ($m=1$) is written as $E = (p+iwx)(p-iwx)$ and this in turn written using the Moyal star product $\{ d/dp \text{ left } d/dx \text{ right} - d/dx \text{ left } d/dp \text{ right} \}$ in terms of a parameter $(\hbar/2)$, one obtains: $E = pp/2 + wwxx/2 + \hbar w/2$ i.e. a semiclassical expression for the quantum result with the ground state energy $\hbar w/2$.

In Part I, we showed that this result follows from combining a time-independent Schrodinger equation in x -space with one in p (momentum) - space. The two second order equations yield second order derivatives composed of two parts. One part returns the form $pp/2m$ and $k/2 xx$ and the other returns a constant which is the ground state energy if one considers the ground state p and x wavefunctions which are of the form $\exp(- (pp/2 + wwxx/2) /b)$ where b is the ground state energy.. The first part cancels with kinetic energy from the p -space equation and $.5kxx$ from the x -space equation. Thus, this combination of two Schrodinger equations really involves three pieces: ((A)) an energy term in p,x , ((B)) a cancellation term of this energy and ((C)) a constant ground state energy term.

In (2) it is stated that the Moyal star product $**$ has the property:

$$\int dx dp f(p,x) g(p,x) = \int dx dp f(p,x) ** g(p,x)$$

This is then used to argue that: $H(p,x) ** f(p,x) = E f(p,x)$ ((1)). For the ground state oscillator case, only the first and second order operator terms contribute. The first order operator term is zero, while the second order term behaves in exactly the same manner as the combined x -space and p -space time-independent Schrodinger equations used in Part I. Thus the combined p and x space time-independent Schrodinger equations for the oscillator Hamiltonian $pp/2 + wwxx/2$ is identical to the Moyal approach.

Argument from Part I

In Part I, we argued that the ground state oscillator wavefunction must be of the form $\exp(-1/b(pp/2 + wwxx/2))$ where $pp/2 + wwxx/2$ is the classical energy for $m=1$ and b is the ground state energy. We then combined the x -space and p -space time-independent Schrodinger equations to obtain:

$$(pp/2 + wwxx/2) W(x)W1(p) - \frac{1}{2} W1(p) \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} - \frac{k}{2} W(x) \frac{d}{dp} \frac{dW1}{dp} = 2E_0 W(x)W1(p)$$

((2))

Here $W(x)$ is the spatial wavefunction and $W1(p)$ the momentum wavefunction.

One may note that ((2)) holds for any energy level. If one assumes $W(x)W1(p) = \exp(-1/b (pp/2 + wwxx/2))$ then the energy level is the ground state one.

As one may see, there are no first order derivative terms, but only second order ones in addition to the first term on the LHS which is classical energy with no derivatives acting upon it. Thus, the second order derivatives each bring back two terms. One is a constant in the oscillator case multiplied by $W(x)W_1(p)$ and the second cancels with a piece of the first term on the LHS of ((2)) i.e. the raw energy term. As a result, the ground state energy follows from a: $pp/2 + wwxx/2$ in the function $W(x)W_1(p)$, but returns only w . This is similar to using one derivative d/dx or d/dp and operating on $p+iwx$, $p-iwx$ i.e. $(p+iwx)$ Moyal product $(p-iwx)$. Only the first term and the first order term of the Moyal operator ** which is:

$\{ d/dp \text{ left } d/dx \text{ right} - d/dx \text{ left } d/dp \text{ right} \}$ ((3)) yields nonzero results.

((2)), however, is a second order equation. It has the appearance of a second order exponential expansion with the first order term being 0, with derivatives acting in the Moyal operator fashion. The full Moyal ** star product is:

$$f(x,p) ** g(x,p) = f(x,p) \exp(-i \hbar/2 \{ d/dp \text{ left } d/dx \text{ right} - d/dx \text{ left } d/dp \text{ right} \}) g(x,p) \quad ((3))$$

The second order form of the Schrodinger equation suggests there may be a second Moyal star product equation linked to the oscillator ground state or even other states.

Moyal Star Product Equation for Energy Eigenstates

In (2), it is argued that:

$$\text{Integral } dp \, dx \, g(p,x) f(p,x) = \text{Integral } dp \, dx \, g(p,x) ** f(p,x) \quad ((4))$$

Using $g=H(p,x)$ the classical Hamiltonian and $f(p,x)$ a semiclassical probability function, (2) writes:

$$H(p,x) ** f(p,x) = E f(p,x) \quad ((5))$$

We apply ((5)) to the oscillator ground state. We first note that the Wigner transform for the oscillator ground state is (3):

$$\text{Wigner transform of oscillator gs} = \text{Constant} \exp(-aaxx) \exp(-pp/aa) \quad ((6))$$

((6)) is exactly of the form of $W_0(x) W_1(p)$ i.e. the product of the spatial wavefunction with the momentum one. Furthermore in part 1 we argued that this product must be a function of the classical energy $pp/2 + wwxx/2$ ($m=1$). In (3) it is argued that Wigner transforms of all oscillator energy states are functions of the classical energy.

For ((4)) to hold for $g(p,x)=H(p,x)$, $\text{Integral } f(p,x) (pp/2 + wwxx/2) = \text{average energy}$.

In Part I, we argued that the ground state oscillator $W(x)W_1(p)$ must be a Gaussian in classical energy (like ((6))). Thus $\exp(-(\frac{pp}{2} + \frac{wwxx}{2}) / b)$ is the form and b must be the average energy.

Thus ((5)) should allow one to calculate the oscillator ground state energy. Using the definition ((3)), one may expand the exp in various powers of the Moyal operator. Given that $H(p,x) = \frac{pp}{2} + \frac{wwxx}{2}$ ($m=1$), no combination of d/x d/dp acting on $H(x,p)$ survive and one may only have derivative powers as high as order two (i.e. d/dx d/dx or d/dp d/dp). Thus the exp only needs to be expanded to second order (like the combined Schrodinger equations).

The ground state form of an exponential is used in order to find b which is the ground state energy.

The first term in the exp expansion is 1 which yields: $(\frac{pp}{2} + \frac{wwxx}{2}) f(x,p)$.

The first order operator term is: $\hbar/2 \{ \frac{ww2x}{2} \frac{df}{dp} - 2p \frac{df}{dx} \} = 0$ by the fact that: $f(\frac{pp}{2} + \frac{wwxx}{2})$

The second order operator term is:

$\frac{d}{dx} \text{left} \frac{d}{dx} \text{left} \frac{d}{dp} \text{right} \frac{d}{dp} \text{right} - 2 \frac{d}{dx} \text{left} \frac{d}{dp} \text{left} \frac{d}{dp} \text{right} \frac{d}{dx} \text{right} + \frac{d}{dp} \text{left} \frac{d}{dp} \text{left} \frac{d}{dx} \text{right} \frac{d}{dx} \text{right}$

The mixed term $\frac{d}{dx} \text{left} \frac{d}{dp} \text{left}$ yields 0 because $H(p,x) = \frac{pp}{2} + \frac{wwxx}{2}$. Thus one has:

$2\frac{ww}{2} \frac{d}{dp} \frac{df}{dp} + 2 \frac{d}{dx} \frac{df}{dx}$ from the second order operator term and brings back a constant linked to the ground state energy.

This is identical to the combined Schrodinger equation approach for the ground state.

For the ground state case of $f(p,x) = \exp(-1/b (\frac{pp}{2} + \frac{wwxx}{2}))$, one piece of the second order derivatives $\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx}$, $\frac{d}{dp} \frac{d}{dp}$ lead to cancelation with the first term $\frac{pp}{2} + \frac{wwxx}{2}$, while the second terms yield constant which sum to give b , the ground state energy.

General Energy Levels for the Oscillator

One may note that in general, the expansion of the exp in the star product definition is only to second order for any oscillator energy level in ((5)), not just the ground state. This maps into the idea of using the x-space and p-space time-independent Schrodinger equations. These hold for any energy level, yet only include second order terms. The first order term:

$$\hbar/2 \{ \frac{ww2x}{2} \frac{df}{dp} - 2p \frac{df}{dx} \} = 0$$

Is always 0 regardless of the energy level because $f(\frac{pp}{2} + \frac{wwxx}{2})$.

Thus the combination of an x-space and p-space oscillator time-independent Schrodinger equations for the oscillator ground state is identical to the Moyal approach $H(x,p) \star f(x,p) = E f(x,p)$ of (2).

Another way to say this is that the quantum x and p wavefunction product: $\psi_0(x)\psi_0(p)$ is equivalent to the semiclassical Wigner transform $f(x,p)$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, in (2) it is stated that $H(x,p) \star f(x,p) = E f(x,p)$ where $H(x,p)$ is the classical Hamiltonian and $f(x,p)$ a semiclassical probability scheme. \star represents the Moyal star product which is $H(x,p) \exp(i \hbar/2 \{ d/dx \text{ left } d/dp \text{ right} - d/dp \text{ left } d/dx \text{ right} \})$. Given the form of the oscillator $H(x,p) = p^2/2 + wx^2/2$ ($m=1$), one may expand the exponential only to second order in the Moyal operator. For an oscillator, $f(x,p) = f(p^2/2 + wx^2/2)$ so the first order operator term is 0 i.e. $H(x,p) \{ d/dx \text{ left } d/dp \text{ right} - d/dp \text{ left } d/dx \text{ right} \} f(x,p)$ for any energy level. Thus the first term of the expansion of the exp is: $(p^2/2 + wx^2/2)$, the second is 0 and the third is: $2wx d/dp + 2 d/dx$. This is identical to combining x-space and p-space time-independent Schrodinger equations as done in Part I to find the ground state energy. In the case of the ground state energy, $f(x,p)$ is of the form $\exp(-(p^2/2 + wx^2/2) / b)$ where b is the ground state energy and $H \star f = E_0 f$ may be used to find it. This yields the same result for the ground state energy as using $(p+iwx) \star (p-iwx)$ as shown in Part I.

References

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